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Dystopia

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Dystopia is an imagined society marked by extreme suffering, oppression, or injustice, often under totalitarian rule or societal collapse. The word comes from Greek roots dys (bad) and topos (place), meaning “bad place,” portraying a world where ideals have failed or turned against humanity.

This story was made to avoid, not to be realized

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CHAPTER I: ARTIFICIAL WARS

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The world is heading towards the 6th world war, which is because Joeland suspects that Levistan has a nuclear bomb and is preparing it by refining and combining Milkinium materials. This is not the first time they have slandered another country, 34 years ago Joeland also invaded Sumestan on suspicion of making weapons of mass destruction, which was ultimately not proven.

Levistan is the world's largest producer of oil, coal, and several types of Milkinium. Despite this, Levistan is a generous country as it does not close off exports to countries in need. However, fear and greed overtook Joeland, who feared that Joeland could shut down its exports at any time.

Therefore, this invasion was necessary. However, due to criticism by other countries, they did not carry out the invasion, but instead overthrew the existing government and replaced it with a puppet government that could be controlled at any time by them.

With the puppet government in control, Red Bank was able to take control of Levistan's central bank and became a savior figure for improving the economy and inflation conditions there.

Long story short, Levistan's government was overthrown, but there's a civil war that required most Levistan citizens to flee to Billland. This is not good, considering that the large number of refugees can damage the country's system, and unfortunately this is intentional by Joeland.

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With Billand's society broken, their government is unstable. Exacerbated by the death of their leader, Joeland can easily provide a new leader who can be controlled from behind the scenes.

Thus, Joeland has controlled the entire world from behind the scenes. All central banks have been owned by their Bank, all world leaders, both from coalition parties and opposition parties. This is because they are the ones who control the economy, they manage the system and the flow of the economy, so bribing these leaders with money, lust, pride, or other desires is easy.

Everyone says and promises that they will not commit corruption, but will eradicate it, yet none of them can maintain their integrity and principles when presented with instant gratification. This is the end of the beginning.

Thus concludes this first part.

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CHAPTER II: SOCIETY 5.0 & MORAL DECAY

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The war ended, and society slowly began to enter the society 5.0 stage. Keep in mind that society 5.0 is a social system with technology at the center, not humans. Thus, the development of science and technology does not correlate linearly with the quality of life of humans, especially those who are not rich.

Most jobs are replaced by technology. This causes a huge gap between the rich and the poor. Making the poor poorer, and the rich richer.

The poor are forced to take up illegal jobs to earn a living, or do things that are not allowed by law or religion, bypassing morals and ethics to survive.

As this happens over and over again, the poor feel that their prayers are not answered by God, so over time, they begin to distrust God and abandon religion.

Likewise, those who are rich feel that they were the best, have high pride, live in stable and eternal enjoyment. So they feel that religion is just a barrier to get pleasure and God's presence is no longer needed.

Thus concludes the second part.

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CHAPTER III: ZERO FAITH

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The number of believers and religious people decreased, but animist and dynamist beliefs suddenly increased again. The believers, regardless of religion, who still clung to moral values, ethics, virtue, and empathy gathered in one country, namely Johnstan.

They thought that gathering in one country would make it easier for them to fight the godless pagans and idolaters. However, they were wrong. Before the war started, they were nuked by the Joelands. They said: *'You will fuse your nucleotides into soup, before God and His prophet come to save you!'*. And so the believers were counted on their fingers, some of whom began to abandon their religion.

Thus concludes the third part.

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CHAPTER IV: MORAL NIHILISM

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Everyone keep following their egos, forgetting moral values. There are more and more rules, more and more specific in every area of human life, but of course more and more are broken. Because they only know what not to do, not why not to do it.

This is the main bridge of human civilisation to moral nihilism. As more and more poor people kept being born, one of the rich men offered them a job. But this job was not just any job.

The rich came up with a cheap invasive brain-computer interface (BCI) that could control the human brain to do what it needs to do, such as work. With this, they can save a lot of money instead of continuing to make sophisticated and expensive robots and AI, especially since the natural resources for making these things are depleting, which makes the production cost more expensive.

This makes humans into three groups: the rich, those *slave* who live with BCIs, and the poor. Those who are tired of living in a dilapidated society are willing to sell their free will to be implanted with the BCI in order to survive. They felt it was the only option they could choose. Not only that, animism and dynamism beliefs are increasing among the poor.

Thus concludes the fourth part.

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CHAPTER V:
JOE'S REGIME

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The worship of gods increased among the rich and the poor. The Joelands, who controlled most of the companies and businesses worshipped Moloch, the rich but not the Joes worshipped Baphomet, while the poor believed in dynamism, believing that some objects had the power and validity to grant their wishes. But there are also Elysians, people who try to live with morals and ethics and control their desires, but due to the influence of a very bad society, their existence is slowly disappearing.

Those who are rich, but not Joes, think that they will always be rich and stable, and will never become poor. But they were wrong. One day, the Joelanders felt that the rich non-Joe could become a threat one day. They therefore planned to take over everything they owned, and of course no one could stop them, because not only did they have a genius strategy to maintain their absolute power, but also because they regularly made offerings to Moloch, one of which was to sacrifice aborted fetuses.

To make a long story short, they took their daughters. Children under the age of 15 were forced to become sex slaves for those barbarians. And those who refuse will be implanted with BCI. Those above 15 would be impregnated and put into tubes containing artificial amniotic acid, which were also connected to an automated milking system that took their breast milk. Those unfortunate children become their display and collection. They also routinely aborted them, which were then offered to Moloch. And then impregnate them again. An endless cycle of suffering.

Thus concludes the fifth part.

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CHAPTER VI:
LUCIFER'S PROPHECY

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After tremendous chaos, especially among the poor. The few rich people who were not massacred were thrown into the same society as those with poor people. They now lived side by side with the people they had avoided, oppressed, humiliated and abused. The deep-seated hatred that the poor people had made them return what they had earned.

They tortured them, then beheaded them, and mass raped their wives and daughters on the highway. They blamed these formerly rich non-Joes for the suffering they had endured.

Once upon a time, one of the daughters of this once rich family looked for a way to escape this problem. She was a beautiful, beautiful virgin. She found a book that had been written by the cult of Lucifer, which had long been lost. She thought of creating a cult to take refuge in it, and take revenge on the Joes.

He wanted to build that Lucifer cult and summon Lucifer to earth, but he was at a loss as to how to do such a complex thing. Then he saw his reflection in a puddle by the roadside. He realised that he could use his body to get cult members. So he started looking for and gathering members for his cult and spreading his teachings. Those who joined the cult could enjoy her body for free. When she got her first member and did it for the first time, the moment her hymen broke, she cried out in pain and hatred, and cursed Joe's people.

Thus concludes the sixth part.

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CHAPTER VII:
THE GREAT WAR AMONG INFIDELS

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Long story short, after years of trying to serve almost billions of men and women with her body, she managed to build a cult of Lucifer and now plans to summon him in order to avenge what happened so far. In the revelation book of Lucifer's teachings that he found earlier, it says that they must sacrifice 666 thousand not older than 8-month-old baby foetuses, right on the full moon. Which will then be eaten together as a sign of unity with Lucifer.

She prepared the necessary things and made the offering to Lucifer. After the spell was cast and all the rituals were performed to summon Lucifer, nothing seemed to change. Lucifer did not appear that day. The woman was afraid, because it seemed as if she had deceived many people into a futile cult. In her fear, she thought of pretending that Lucifer had appeared. The other people in the cult could not see anything, but because of her actions, mass delusion ensued, with people believing that Lucifer was there just because they were afraid that if they could not see him, something terrible would happen. So they unitedly bowed down to the fictional Lucifer.

The woman seemed to be resaying the words of Lucifer, who told them to slaughter the Joes. The masses of them did just that. Surprised by the unexpected, the Joes launched nuclear bombs, gases of mass destruction, and dangerous viruses all over the world. Then the apocalypse happened.

Thus concludes the seventh part.

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CHAPTER VIII:
POST APOCALYPSE ODYSSEY

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Tired of the behaviour of these unbelievers, God was too lazy to save them because He felt they were not worth saving. The two warring parties were not believers, fighting for others. They fought out of spite, hatred, and selfishness. Even though He had promised not to destroy life on Earth, signalled by the rainbow in the sky, mankind still destroyed themselves. Joe's side was drowning in greed and selfishness, while Lucifer's followers were drowning in hatred. Even after all mankind had turned away from God and worshipped other things, He still had hope in them. Nonetheless, we disappointed Him. Humans are indeed failures, God was so disappointed in them. Mankind was no longer worthy of the stage and thus no longer worth saving.

Although almost all life on earth has been wiped out, there are still some living things that have survived. Like *Cladosporium* and *Deinococcus radiodurans* that survived the nukes. And it is from them that life and civilization on Earth will be created again, and will return to its original state. There will be replacements for the plants, animals, and even humans that are radiosynthetic creatures. Nature always finds a way to survive. This is what distinguishes living beings from demons, living beings want their civilization to survive and will try to get it, while demons want themselves to survive forever. This selfishness and egoism, when possessed by humans, makes them not much different from the devil.

Thus concludes the last part.